

WP1 Assessment tool for water governance innovations v2

GOVAQUA Deliverable 1.3

**Gül Özerol, Jyri Mustajoki, César Casiano Flores, Ulf Stein,
Joanne Vinke-de Kruijf, Suvi Sojamo, Antti Belinskij**

**Governance innovations for a transition to sustainable
and equitable water use in Europe.**

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Authors:	Gül Özerol, Jyri Mustajoki, César Casiano Flores, Ulf Stein, Joanne Vinke-de Kruijf, Suvi Sojamo, Antti Belinskij
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Summary

The overall goal of the GOVAQUA project is to identify, assess, develop and validate water governance innovations to support and accelerate a transition towards sustainable and equitable water use in Europe. In work package (WP) 1 of the project, we have built a conceptual framework and, based on it, developed the GOVAQUA assessment tool for systematically assessing how the broader water governance context affects the design, uptake and implementation of the innovations. The tool is being co-created and tested by the six Living Labs of the project in 2024-2026, providing empirical insights not only for developing the innovations in question but also for the further refinement and finalisation of the tool. The results of the tool application will also contribute towards the ultimate goal of the project, which is to validate good practices of innovative water governance and to co-create detailed and contextualised transition pathways to reach the broader policy aims.

The GOVAQUA assessment tool comprises multi-dimensional and cross-sectoral criteria and indicators that build on existing assessment approaches and integrate the thematic innovation approaches covered in other WPs of GOVAQUA. The development of the tool was an iterative process. First, an initial set of criteria and indicators were identified through a review of relevant literature and policies. To get a comprehensive view of the different ways to assess governance innovations in water management in the literature, we first reviewed existing assessment approaches. We also analysed the relevant policy targets both at the EU and global level, focusing on the targets of the Water Framework Directive (WFD), European Green Deal (EGD; especially EU Biodiversity and Adaptation Strategies and the EU Mission Ocean and Waters), and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs, especially SDG6 on Water and Sanitation).

The first version of the assessment tool was discussed in an expert workshop with representatives from all project partners and three External Advisory Board members. The main questions discussed in the workshop were: 1) what criteria and indicators should be included in the assessment, 2) how well the indicators meet the principles of good indicators (of which relevance, understandability, scalability and transferability were seen as most relevant), 3) what assessment scales should be used on each indicator, and 4) how well the indicators support the targets of WFD, EGD and SDG. The final version of the assessment tool consists of 32 indicators classified into nine criteria and 32 indicators. A four-point scale is applied to assess each indicator. The assessment indicators are accompanied by open-ended questions to describe the baseline status of the governance regime.

The tool is intended to be applied twice in GOVAQUA within the scope of WP6, which focuses on Living Labs. The first application is carried out at the start (i.e. the Exploration phase) of the GOVAQUA Living Labs in 2024. In this application, the current status of the governance regime is assessed to diagnose the current status and set ambitions for a desired water governance future. After this initial application, a representative and complementary set of innovations are explored and experimented within the Living Labs. The second application will take place at the end of the Living Lab processes, in 2026, to garner insights on the added value of the innovations to improve the status of the governance in that particular regime (i.e., the Evaluation and Feedback phase of the Living Labs). After being tested and finalised, the tool will be openly accessible for use in different basin settings. The primary end-users of the tool are water managers and other relevant stakeholders at the basin or catchment level. The tool is meant to assist them with 1) identifying the strengths and weaknesses of the current water governance regime; and 2) focusing their efforts on improving practices with regard to the most relevant and urgent issues. As the assessment is conducted at the level of the governance regime, within which the innovation is designed and implemented, the tool is suitable to address any type of governance innovation. When applying the tool, end-users are encouraged to engage national-level stakeholders that have responsibility and decision-making power in the broader water management and governance processes.

This report is an updated and expanded version of the Deliverable 1.2 Assessment Tool v1. It consists of a brief review of the existing assessment approaches and relevant policy targets, the development process of the tool, the description of the elements of the tool, and the initial results and observations from the first application of the tool by the Living Labs.

1. Introduction

Main policy documents on the European and global levels, such as the Water Framework Directive (WFD), European Green Deal (EGD) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), have set goals and specific targets to improve water sustainability. To reach those targets, new innovations in water and water-related sectors have been called for (EC, 2019; EEA, 2019). Innovations are defined as “the use of new ideas, products or methods where they have not been used before” (EUROSTAT, n.d.), and can be related to both the process of innovating and the product of that process. In transition studies, innovation is understood as a “transformation towards a sustainable society, as a response to a number of persistent problems confronting contemporary modern societies” (Grin et al., 2010, p. 1). Within the context of the GOVAQUA project, we define **water governance innovations as instruments, approaches and arrangements that have the potential to accelerate a transition to sustainable and equitable water use in Europe.**

Through the GOVAQUA project, we aim to identify, assess, develop and validate such innovations. The project consists of eight work packages (WPs), four of which analyse and compare water governance innovations with thematic focuses: legal and regulatory approaches (WP2), participatory and collaborative approaches (WP3), economic and financial approaches (WP4), and digital approaches (WP5). Each of these WPs cover various governance instruments, for example:

- WP2: instruments for reconciling water uses, implementation of e-flows and regulating value chains and sustainable water footprints;
- WP3: multi-stakeholder collaboration across levels and sectors, empowerment and involvement of citizens, and the engagement of private companies;
- WP4: water markets, tariffs, water pricing and impact investments;
- WP5: open data initiatives and tools supporting data generation, enabling data sharing and the improvement of decision-making and governance.

GOVAQUA further houses six Living Labs (WP6) in diverse geographical contexts and governance arrangements in six selected locations in Europe: Crau Aquifer in France, Archipelago Sea Basin in Finland, Axarquía Region in Spain, River Thames in the UK, Nordic Hydropower in Finland and Sweden, and the Dunavăț Region in the Danube delta Romania. Through the Living Labs, a **representative and complementary set of innovations** are explored, experimented with, and evaluated by key stakeholders and experts. Examples of innovations being developed within the Living Labs include water markets, water stewardship and innovative financing mechanisms, water user participation, citizen science, and drought management plans.

This report focusing on the **GOVAQUA assessment tool for water governance innovations** is a deliverable of WP1 and its positioning and links within the overall framework of the GOVAQUA project is illustrated in Figure 1 below. **The main objective of WP1 is to define, assess and advance the transition towards sustainable and equitable water governance at multiple levels and across multiple sectors.** We adapt the broadly cited definition of Rogers and Hall (2003, p.16) of water governance consisting of “the range of political, social, economic and administrative systems that are in place to develop and manage water resources, and the delivery of water services” complementing it with environmental protection and covering also governance systems beyond the traditional water sector, i.e., sectors with major direct or indirect water use or impacts.

Sustainable and equitable water governance enables sustainable and equitable water use as the normative goal of water transitions. We understand **sustainable water use** as “the use of water that supports the ability of human society to endure and flourish into the indefinite future without undermining the integrity of the hydrological cycle or the ecological systems that depend on it” (Gleick, 2000, p. 131). **Equitable water use** refers to a fair water allocation from a societal perspective, going beyond environmental sustainability and resource efficiency (Hoekstra, 2014).

To reach the objective of WP1, we i) build a **conceptual framework of water transitions**, ii) develop and apply a **tool for assessing how the broader governance regime affects innovative approaches**, iii) systematically **compare innovative approaches**, iv) **synthesise the results** from the whole project, and v)

co-create transition pathways to reach the broader policy aims. This report addresses the second step. It presents the GOVAQUA assessment tool that has been designed for systematically assessing how the broader water governance context affects the design, uptake and implementation of the innovations.

Figure 1. Positioning of the assessment tool and this report in the overall framework of the GOVAQUA project.

The GOVAQUA assessment tool addresses the urgent need for comprehensive approaches. While cross-sectoral integration is widely promoted in water governance, sectoral silos and politics, as well as power asymmetries, prevail in practice (Allouche et al. 2015., Endo et al. 2017; Purwanto et al. 2021). As elaborated in chapter 2, existing approaches to assess water governance fail to respond to the need for a sustainability transition within and beyond the water sector. We address these scientific and policy knowledge gaps in two ways. First, we advance water governance assessments by developing a comprehensive assessment tool in collaboration with the Living Labs. The application of the tool will create insights from across Europe on the challenges and levers for integrating the diverse needs and interests of multiple actors and sectors. In addition, it can help to assess progress towards a sustainable and equitable water use. Second, by examining and assessing water governance regimes across multiple sectors, we will enhance the understanding of the linkages and dependencies within and among sectors that need reconciliation to achieve sustainable and equitable water use. By actively involving stakeholders in the Living Labs, we will co-create practical insights for different river basin settings. Together, these insights contribute towards solving direct and indirect sustainability challenges in water governance as presented in the WFD, EGD and SDGs.

The GOVAQUA assessment tool comprises **multi-dimensional and cross-sectoral criteria and indicators** that build on existing assessment approaches and integrate the thematic innovation approaches covered in WPs 2-5. It offers a unique perspective to assess how the water governance regime at the catchment or basin level impacts the design and implementation of a specific innovation and its contribution to sustainable and equitable water use. Within the scope of WP 6, the GOVAQUA Living Labs will apply the tool twice: the first time in 2024 to assess their current situation, to set ambitions for a desired water governance future, and to inform the innovation selection and design, and a second time in 2026 to assess their progress with the innovation, reflect on lessons learned, and, if needed, reconsider their ambitions.

After being tested and finalised, the tool will be made openly available for use in different river basin settings. Given its scientific scope, this report targets academic audiences, whereas the tool itself is a user-oriented product that will target potential end-users, who mainly include water managers and other relevant stakeholders at the basin or catchment level. Before publishing the tool, additional attention will be paid to make it accessible for end-users. The tool and its relevant documentation will be published on the project website and the GOVAQUA Online Academy.

The remaining chapters of the report are organised as follows. Chapter 2 presents the review results of existing assessment approaches. Chapter 3 presents the policy targets at the EU and global levels. Chapter 4 lays out the GOVAQUA assessment tool, including its design process, content and application process. Finally, chapter 5 presents the initial results and observations from the application of the assessment tool by the Living Labs. Further information about the existing frameworks and targets, as well as guidance for describing the baseline governance situation and applying the assessment tool, and the list of assessment questions and scores are provided in appendices.

2. Review of Existing Assessment Approaches

This chapter provides an overview of existing assessment tools, methods and frameworks, hereafter “approaches”, which offer potentially relevant dimensions, criteria or indicators for the GOVAQUA assessment tool.

Various assessment approaches exist related to water governance, as shown in a review conducted in the early 2010s (UNDP, 2013). These approaches have been designed for different purposes. Thus, their applicability depends much on the needs of the cases being assessed and how their initial purposes fit in with these needs. The approaches can be characterised at least based on the following features:

- **Process- vs. content-oriented approaches:** Some approaches focus on supporting the actual assessment process (*How the process should be conducted?*), whereas others focus on the content of the case (*What should be taken into account?*)
- **Generic approaches vs. approaches focusing on certain substance:** Some approaches are generic in a sense that they can be applied in almost any field, whereas some approaches are designed to a certain application area taking into account the characteristics of that area.
- **Comprehensive vs. task-specific approaches:** Some approaches focus on getting a comprehensive overall picture of the problem, which can be quite abstract, whereas others provide concrete support for certain tasks of the process, such as evaluating alternatives.

In practice, these three features are not strict, and most of the existing assessment approaches have elements of both ends of each feature. Nevertheless, it is useful to be aware of these dimensions to understand the possible restrictions of the approaches in certain cases. The approaches included in the review have been selected based on relevance, i.e., whether they offer a comprehensive framework (set of dimensions, criteria or indicators) that can be applied for assessing the governance regime of a river basin/catchment, and whether they pay attention to other aspects or concepts regarding water governance and the sustainability transition in the water sector.

The remainder of this chapter presents the reviewed approaches, describing their conceptual basis, if applicable, the dimensions, criteria and indicators that they use, and a reflection on their conceptual, methodological, or empirical limitations for the purposes of the GOVAQUA assessment tool. We first elaborate on **four approaches that are relevant for GOVAQUA purposes**, starting with the **OECD Water Governance Indicator Framework**, which has been known and applied widely, and then three approaches which the GOVAQUA project team members have co-developed and/or applied in previous projects, namely the **Governance Assessment Tool**, the **STEER Conceptual Framework**, and the **Water Sensitive Cities Index** applied in the [CATCH](#), an Interreg North Sea Region project on urban water management and climate adaptation. For the sake of focus and brevity, detailed information about the elements of the reviewed approaches are presented in Appendix A. Finally, we introduce other approaches that might offer relevant criteria or indicators for the GOVAQUA assessment tool.

2.1. OECD Water Governance Indicator Framework

The OECD water governance indicator framework comprises **12 principles across the dimensions of efficiency, effectiveness, and trust and engagement** (OECD, 2015). The principles included in each dimension are shown in Figure A1 in Appendix A. This framework focuses on water governance policy frameworks (what), institutions (who) and instruments (how). For each principle, the policy frameworks, institutions and instruments are operationalised as three indicators.

An assessment methodology has been built based on the framework, including three phases (preparation, diagnosis and action), and a **self-assessment toolkit for each principle** (OECD, 2018). The terminology and guidance offered by the framework is **practice-oriented**, thus need little tailoring for use by practitioners. However, the framework also has limitations that hinder its applicability for GOVAQUA purposes. First, while it contains relevant criteria and indicators for assessing water governance and a specific principle focusing on innovative governance, it pays little attention to the systemic transition needed in the water and related sectors towards sustainable and equitable water use. Second, while the framework calls for an

inclusive approach to the assessment process, it has an inherent focus on the role of governmental organizations, with most principles centred around the levels and functions of governmental authorities (Akhmouch et al., 2018). Third, the framework is meant to be applicable at local, basin or national levels, but its application at non-national levels has been limited so far (cf. Martín Velasco et al., 2023).

2.2. Governance Assessment Tool

The Governance Assessment Tool (GAT) is based on a conceptualisation of **governance as a 'structural context'**, or a 'regime' that underlies the given policy field and the societal sectors that are relevant for the implementation of policy measures, strategies or projects (Bressers, 2009). The governance regime is described along **five dimensions** that reflect the multiplicities of governance: 1) administrative levels and spatial scales, 2) actors and networks included or excluded in the implementation process, 3) problem perspectives and goal ambitions regarding the policy field, 4) strategies and instruments for institutional change, and 5) the responsibilities and resources allocated for implementation (Bressers and Kuks, 2003). The assessment of the regime starts by describing the five dimensions (the questions that are typically used for this description are shown in Appendix A, Table A1). The governance regime can be to some degree **supportive** and to some degree **restrictive** for implementation. GAT uses **four criteria** to assess this degree from complementary perspectives: 1) extent (also called 'completeness', 2) coherence, 3) flexibility and intensity (also called 'pressure for change'). The criteria are applied by asking multiple questions for each dimension, based on a matrix form, as shown in Appendix A, Table A2.

The GAT has been applied in **diverse contexts**, such as urban water transition in the Netherlands (Casiano Flores et al., 2023), wastewater governance in Mexico (Casiano Flores et al., 2017), water conservation in Iran (Mirnezami et al., 2019), water governance in Palestine (Judeh et al., 2017), and coastal innovations in England (Vikolainen et al., 2017), as well as in policy fields outside water. As comparative analyses have gained importance in water governance (Özerol et al., 2018), the applications of GAT also include multiple cases, such as wastewater policy implementation in three Mexican sub-national cases (Casiano Flores et al., 2019); urban water management innovations in Denmark, Germany, and Spain (Rouillard et al., 2016), and the actors of drought governance in Belgium, France, Germany, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom (Özerol, 2019).

Questions included in the GAT have been typically answered by researchers familiar with policy and governance concepts. Reflections on the accessibility and applicability of the GAT by practitioners have recently led to the development of a **practitioners' version** (Özerol and Bressers, 2023). This version enables the practitioners to conduct a self-assessment by answering 20 closed questions with five possible answers. While the GAT has been applied to assess multiple governance levels and become more practitioner-oriented over time, it still pays little attention to the transition towards sustainable and equitable water use. Therefore, its direct applicability for GOVAQUA assessment purposes is limited.

2.3. STEER Conceptual Framework

The main objective of the STEER conceptual framework is to provide a deeper understanding of **how governance and management system characteristics influence its performance**. This framework also examines how these relationships are affected by the surrounding social and environmental conditions (see Figures A2 and A3 in Appendix A for the central elements of this framework).

The STEER framework emphasises results linked to actualized coordination and collaboration, as well as social learning and resolving conflicts. As defined by Koontz and Thomas (2006) and OECD (2002), **impacts** refer to the extensive and lasting effects produced by various **outcomes** on society or broader environmental, economic, and social conditions. These effects can be direct or indirect, intentional or unintentional. Indicators for measuring these impacts might be tailored to specific contexts, depending on the goals of water governance and management, like improving water quality to meet regulatory standards. Alternatively, they might be based on universally accepted standards, such as sustainability principles related to water security. The aforementioned processes are illustrated as networks of action situations (see Figure A4 in Appendix A). The concept of an action situation, central to the institutional

analysis and development (IAD) framework, was originally introduced by Elinor Ostrom in 2005. STEER adopts a broader interpretation of this concept (see Table A3 in Appendix A for the governance functions that characterize various types of action situations representing planning and implementation processes.)

Each single **action situation** can be assigned to one of the following **phases**:

- **Planning** refers to strategic and operational planning and procedures in different sectors established to develop and revise strategic and operational plans. Planning also includes the establishment of procedures to facilitate and control implementation.
- **Implementation** refers to putting a more abstract policy, plan or rule into operation by developing specific measures. It also comprises capacity building for implementation. Implementation activities produce results that are of direct relevance for operational activities interfering with the physical environment, which are specified as ecosystem services interactions.
- **Ecosystem services interactions** refer to direct interference with the resource. On the one hand, this includes operational activities of resource users that are based on contributions from ecosystems. On the other hand, it refers to activities that result in tangible changes in ecosystem services or physical objects like infrastructure. Such activities can but need not necessarily include deliberate management activities.

2.4. Urban Water Management Transitions Framework

The Urban Water Management Transitions Framework (UWMTF) was developed by Brown et al. (2008). This framework sees water as a driving force in the evolution of urban areas and proposes a typology of six different city-states. The UWMTF identifies the **key features of sustainable urban water practices, which can be used to benchmark cities**. The traditional progression involves advancing through prior stages to reach a ‘water-sensitive city’ (WSC) state (see Figure 2). The concept of WSC was developed under the idea that, nowadays, the largest part of the population lives in urban areas, and it is necessary to transition to sustainable water management at the city level. A WSC has a comprehensive cycle for managing water resources, is resistant to climate change, and has a multifunctional infrastructure and urban design that encourages water-sensitive behaviour (Brodnik et al., 2018). The city transition implies governance challenges that need to be considered to support the transition; lack of this consideration can create bottlenecks that hinder the process (Casiano et al., 2023).

Figure 2. Urban Water Management Transitions Framework (Source: Brown et al., 2008)

As part of the tools to support cities' transition, a **WSC Index** was also developed. The WSC index benchmarks cities' water management to identify **strengths and weaknesses in social, technical and ecological aspects** (Wong et al., 2020). It includes seven thematic goals that are assessed using a total of 34 indicators that characterised a WSC. The indicators are scored from 1 to 5, and they are designed to allow users to measure progress towards a WSC state (see Table A4 in Appendix A for the goals and indicators).

Within the scope of the CATCH project, the WSC index has been tailored to the conditions of midsize cities in the North Sea Region by developing a **self-assessment tool** for water managers in local and regional authorities (Özerol et al., 2020). The CATCH self-assessment tool categorizes the indicators with respect to the three pillars of the WSC approach (see Table A5 in Appendix A for an overview of the indicators included in each pillar).

2.5. Other Relevant Concepts and Approaches

The concept of **water justice** acknowledges the inherent power relations within water governance (Sultana, 2018). Such justice considerations are related to a broad range of **political and social factors, which are intersectionally experienced based on e.g., gender, race, income, or indigeneity** (Harris et al., 2017). Justice consists of several dimensions: recognitional (how diverse stakeholders and their needs are recognized), distributive (how a resource is meant to be distributed), and procedural (how the decision-making process is structured) (Lukasiewicz and Baldwin, 2017), restorative justice adding a further layer to all of them (Neal et al. 2014). The field of water justice thus strives to **identify unjust situations based on normative principles** (Zwarteveen and Boelens, 2014). Such reasoning is mirrored in the normative rationale for multi-stakeholder collaboration and public participation, as also specifically addressed in GOVAQUA WP3. Here, the normative rationale relates to justice and equity concerns regarding the participants, processes and outcomes (Fiorino, 1990; Stirling, 2006). It asserts that engagement is necessary for democracies and serves norms such as empowerment, equity, and justice (Vinke-de Kruijf & Özerol, 2013). Neal et al. (2014) provide building blocks for a water justice framework, and Grafton et al. (2022) highlight guiding questions to interrogate causes of water injustice. Polycentric government arrangements have been proposed to achieve stronger and resilient institutions (Ostrom, 2010), making just outcomes more likely (Neal et al., 2014).

Water security is a concept that is closely related to water governance (e.g., Cook and Bakker, 2012). On the one hand, water security assessments can help in **assessing and clarifying governance priorities** (defined e.g., in OECD Water Governance Indicator Framework), but on the other hand, well-functioning governance with integrative assessments reflecting various water uses and users is a prerequisite for water security (Ahopelto, Sojamo et al., 2023). There are also **various approaches** in the field of water security. For example, Marttunen et al. (2019) introduce a framework for assessing water security and the water–energy–food nexus, which provides criteria hierarchy and indicators for assessing water security and support for linking these assessments to other nexus elements (food and energy), as well as support for analysing the assessments in connection to legislation and current level of knowledge. In addition, the framework provides procedural support for carrying out the assessments. Another example is the Urban Water Security Dashboard of 56 indicators based on the pressure-state-impact-response framework (van Ginkel et al., 2018). Doeffinger et al. (2020) introduce a water security dashboard for country scale. The Water Security Diagnostic Framework addresses governance, water-related risks, resource management and service delivery and can be applied at national or regional levels (World Bank, 2021).

Integrated Water Resources Management (IWRM) focuses on looking at water in a broader context in an integrative manner (Rahaman and Varis, 2005). **Water related problems are multi-dimensional, multi-sectoral and multi-regional**, and there are multiple interests, agendas and causes involved. Thus, according to IWRM the solutions should also integrate multi-disciplinary and multi-institutional approaches and multiple stakeholders should participate at all the levels of the processes (Biswas, 2008). IWRM can be seen as a predecessor to WEF nexus thinking (see below) in a sense that both focus on looking at a “big picture” of the problem. The linkages to food and energy are also noted in IWRM, but they are not in such a central role as in the WEF nexus.

The **City Blueprint** approach focuses on the city level and provides insights into the implementation of IWRM and integrated urban water management (IUWM) in practice (Koop and Van Leeuwen, 2015). It brings together three frameworks that together address multi-sectoral aspects of water management: 1) The Trends and Pressures Framework assesses the broader environmental, financial, and social challenges, on which cities often have no influence. 2) The City Blueprint Framework analyses the performance and bottlenecks of IWRM and IUWM, using indicators on water services, wastewater treatment, infrastructure, water quality, solid waste treatment, climate robustness and governance. 3) The Governance Capacity Framework assesses the status of governance along three dimensions, namely knowing (awareness, useful knowledge, and continuous learning), wanting (stakeholder engagement, policy ambition, and agents of change), and enabling (multi-level networks, financial viability, and implementing capacity).

Water–Energy–Food (WEF) nexus is a framework that highlights the linkages between these elements that should be taken into account when considering actions related to any of these elements (e.g., Endo et al., 2017; D’Odorico, 2018). As a concept, the WEF nexus is very broad: on the one hand, it can be interpreted as a general **framework to ensure the transformation from sectoral thinking to integrated one**, but on the other, it provides a **variety of tools** for assessing the complex and systemic interlinkages between the nexus elements (e.g., Albrecht et al., 2018; Dargin et al., 2019). The basic WEF nexus has also been extended to cover other fields of society, including climate, transportation, biodiversity and health (Kim et al., 2023).

van Rijswijk et al. (2014) propose an interdisciplinary approach based on **building blocks**, which aims to assess water shortage, water quality and flood risks. The conceptual foundations of the approach lie in water system analysis, economics, law and public administration. The approach consists of three elements of water governance processes (content, organisation and implementation), and **10 building blocks of water governance**: 1. water system knowledge, 2. values, principles, policy discourses, 3. stakeholders involvement, 4. trade-offs between social objectives, 5. responsibility, authority, means, 6. regulations and agreements, 7. financial arrangements, 8. engineering and monitoring, 9. enforcement, and 10. conflict prevention and resolution. The approach aspires to be of a diagnostic nature, with multiple questions formulated as criteria to assess each building block. However, it doesn’t offer any scoring of the criteria.

Ecosystem services is a concept for examining the links between the functioning of ecosystems and human well-being, defined as an **ability of ecosystems to produce human welfare benefits** (Fischer et al., 2009). In this framework, ecosystem services are typically divided under three (or sometimes four) main classes such as provisioning services (such as drinking water), regulation and maintenance services (such as regulation of the condition of freshwaters) and cultural services (such as recreational interactions with natural environment). The aim is to help quantifying and making visible the **trade-offs between economic interests, and the nature-related benefits and immaterial goods**, which often remain undervalued, for example, in economic valuation approaches (Turkelboom et al., 2018). The framework also provides various lists and classifications of different services as well as indicators for assessing the status of these services (e.g. CICES V5.1., Haines-Young and Potschin-Young, 2018). Many of the services are related to water, which makes them potentially applicable in the GOVAQUA context.

There are also various approaches to procedurally support policy/decision-making processes. These are typically based on the cyclic nature of the process, meaning that in terms of effectiveness, evaluation and monitoring of the actions should be an integral part of the process of good governance. For example, Howlett (2022) defines the **policy-making cycle** as: 1) Agenda setting, 2) Policy formulation, 3) Decision making, 4) Policy implementation, 5) Policy evaluation. A similar cycle has been introduced within the concept of **Structured Decision Making (SDM)** (Gregory et al., 2012) as 1) Define the decision context, 2) Clarify objectives and performance measures, 3) Develop alternatives, 4) Estimate consequences, 5) Evaluate trade-offs, 6) Decide, 7) Implement, monitor & learn. Typically, some kind of **Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA)** tools are utilised in different phases of the SDM process, especially in supporting making trade-offs transparently (e.g., Cegan, 2017). In the Living Lab literature, innovation cycle covers similar phases including 1) Initiation 2) Exploration 3) Experimentation and 4) Evaluation and feedback (Rădulescu et al., 2022, Sojamo et al., 2023). Despite the minor differences in the phases of the cycle, the idea of all the related approaches is the same: through systematic identification, structuring, analysing and monitoring it is possible to increase the quality of decision-making and to make it transparent.

3. Policy Targets at the EU and Global Levels

By using the GOVAQUA assessment tool, the Living Labs will be able to assess the current status of their governance context and set ambitions for a desired water future. To set relevant and realistic ambitions, it is important to be aware of the overarching policy targets at the EU and global levels, particularly the WFD, SDG6 and EGD. However, it could be challenging to use those targets as indicators for the assessment tool due to several reasons. For instance, the impacts of innovations being developed in the Living Labs will probably only be seen after many years, spanning beyond the project timeframe. It can be necessary to prioritise policy targets at different levels according to the local context, taking into account national policy targets as well. Recognizing the limitations and importance of higher-level targets, **this chapter provides a review of the policy targets of the WFD, the EGD and SDG6 that can be translated into assessment criteria.** In general, many water policy goals are not commonly known to stakeholders. Thus, we focus on the main water policy pieces and their targets that are relevant from a governance perspective.

3.1. WFD and Related Targets

The Water Framework Directive (WFD, 2000/60/EC) serves as a **pivotal piece of European Union water policy, emphasizing the long-term sustainability and equity of water resources.** It, along with its supplementary Groundwater Directive (2006/118/EC) and the Environmental Quality Standards Directive (2008/105/EC), forms a comprehensive framework aimed at the protection, enhancement, and restoration of European water bodies. The WFD integrates with other directives, including those focused on bathing water, drinking water, urban wastewater, nitrates pollution, flood risk management, and marine strategies, to promote sustainable water governance through binding targets and institutional monitoring, fostering innovations that influence local and sectoral water management practices. The directive encourages the **active participation of stakeholders** in implementing its objectives, which include maintaining or improving the ecological and chemical status of surface and groundwater, ensuring sustainable water use, and implementing cost recovery principles for water services.

Despite the ambitious goals set by the WFD, with a deadline initially set for 2015 (extendable to 2027 under specific conditions) for **all water bodies to achieve “good status”**, challenges persist. By 2018, only about 40% of European surface waters met the criteria for good ecological or chemical status, although groundwater bodies fared better in terms of quantity and quality. The obstacles to achieving these objectives largely stem from hydromorphological alterations, pollution, and atmospheric deposition. Furthermore, the envisioned contribution of public participation to improving water status has been limited (Rimmert et al. 2020). This indicates a significant gap between the directive’s goals and the current state of water bodies across Europe, highlighting the need for intensified efforts and possibly re-evaluated strategies to address these pressing environmental challenges.

Another relevant principle in the WFD is **cost recovery**. This principle is primarily laid out in Article 9 of the WFD, which mandates that Member States must take adequate steps to ensure that water pricing policies include appropriate incentives for users to use water resources efficiently, thereby contributing to the environmental objectives of the directive. The essence of the cost recovery principle is to ensure that the various uses of water are charged in a manner that reflects the true costs of water services, including environmental and resource costs.

Some of the goals or targets of the WFD, such as the ones on water status and cost recovery, have proven difficult to achieve due to local and national challenges. Therefore, ambitions can vary across basins or catchments in terms of the levels to be achieved. In addition, other relevant directives, such as the Flood Directive and the Drinking Water Directive, the Urban Wastewater Directive, the Bathing Waters Directive and the Nitrates Directive can offer additional targets, depending on the water challenges addressed by the governance innovation.

3.2. EGD and Related Targets

The **EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030** (EC, 2020a) is a core part of the EGD, which also aims to support a green recovery after the Covid-19 pandemic. It is a **comprehensive, ambitious and long-term plan to protect nature and reverse the degradation of ecosystems**. Through its specific actions and commitments, it aims to put biodiversity on a path to recovery by 2030. The strategy has one highly relevant target, namely Target 11, which focuses on freshwater ecosystems, with a target of restoring “at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers”. Two main measures build towards this target: 1) removing or adjusting barriers and restoring flood plains by 2023; and 2) reviewing water abstraction and impoundment permits to implement ecological flows and achieve good status or potential of all surface waters by 2027. A key element of the Biodiversity Strategy is the Nature Restoration Law adopted in June 2024 (European Parliament and the Council, 2024). It combines an overarching restoration objective for the long-term recovery of nature with restoration targets for specific habitats and species. Its specific target on “river connectivity” focuses on identifying and removing barriers that prevent the connectivity of surface waters, reiterating the free-flowing rivers target of the Strategy.

Another EGD-related instrument relevant to GOVAQUA is the **EU Mission “Restore our Ocean and Waters”** (EC, 2020b), which is a programme of action under the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme. Although it does not constitute a policy strategy of the EU commission similarly as the EU Biodiversity Strategy does, it provides **five overarching objectives** for 2030: 1) Filling the knowledge and emotional gap, 2) regenerating marine and freshwater ecosystems, 3) zero pollution, 4) decarbonising our ocean, and waters, and 5) revamping governance. These five objectives are mutually supportive and taken together, **the Mission aims to enable the restoration of the water cycle as a whole**. It has two targets that are especially relevant for GOVAQUA, namely Target 3 (30 percent of EU-waters are highly to fully protected), and Target 5 (30 percent of rivers and surface water bodies are renaturalised). Both targets are under the objective “Regenerating marine and water ecosystems” and rely on multiple measures such as towards removing obstacles to sediments flow, reducing pressures on water bodies resulting from abstraction, channelisation and embankments, and improving biodiversity, with an ambition for an EU-wide programme for de-damming rivers.

The **EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change** (‘Adaptation Strategy’) aims to forge a climate-resilient EU as outlined by the 2050 vision (EC, 2021). The strategy applies to the whole policy cycle, with its **four objectives** being to make adaptation 1) smarter, 2) more systemic, 3) swifter, and 4) to step up international action on adaptation to climate change. Ultimately, the Adaption Strategy intends to **instigate mass adaptation actions towards enhanced climate resilience**. Of special relevance to GOVAQUA is the objective on faster climate adaptation, as it explicitly mentions safeguarding the availability of freshwater resources across the EU. The EC wants to achieve this, for example, through an enhanced engagement of the Common Implementation Strategy of the WFD and Flood Directive. Additionally, the use of drought management plans and various economic instruments shall be promoted. This is in line with GOVAQUA’s envisioned experimentation on these innovative instruments in at least one Living Lab, respectively.

Other EGD-related policy documents can offer relevant targets, depending on the local context of the GOVAQUA Living Labs. For instance, the Farm to Fork Strategy and Zero Pollution Action Plan that have targets for nutrients reduction, which can be relevant for the Living Lab in Finland.

3.3. SDG6 Targets

The SDG framework of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development provides an **integrated framework and 17 goals** for balancing the economic, social and environmental dimensions of sustainable development (United Nations, 2015). SDG 6 aims to **“Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all”**. This goal includes several targets and indicators, for example, for achieving universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking and sanitation, implementing integrated water resources management and improving water quality (see Appendix B for the full list of SDG6 targets and indicators). Water is also an integral part of SDG 14 “Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas and marine resources for sustainable development”. Furthermore, water governance is indirectly linked with several other goals, such as Goal 16, “Peace, justice and strong institutions”, and Goal 13, “Climate action”.

The progress made in the EU towards the SDG6 targets is mapped by Hametner et al. (2023). From a governance perspective, only three specific indicators are relevant for the GOVAQUA project, though they might play an important role for the individual Living Labs. These are the indicators 6.3.2 “Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality”, 6.5.1 “Degree of integrated water resources management”, and 6.b.1 “Proportion of local administrative units with established and operational policies and procedures for participation of local communities in water and sanitation management”. The current status in terms of SDG6 progress can be found in UN Water (n.d.) and UN (2023).

4. GOVAQUA Assessment Tool

The GOVAQUA assessment tool is applied to assess the broader governance context (or the *regime*) that affects the specific (or *niche*) innovations taking place in the GOVAQUA Living Labs. As described in the GOVAQUA Living Lab process design document (Sojamo et al., 2023), niche innovations and the broader governance regime can mutually affect each other. The innovations can ‘fit and conform’, being in tune with the regime, or ‘stretch and transform’, demanding structural changes in the regime (Smith and Raven 2012). The relationship between an innovation and its regime can also change over time in three distinct ways: 1) an innovation exerts a considerable influence on the regime (*paving the way for change*), 2) the regime becomes more supportive of the change that is pursued by the innovation (*easy ride*), or 3) the regime increasingly hinders the change that is pursued by the innovation (*roadblock*) (Beers & Van Mierlo, 2017). Applying the tool at various points in time can provide stakeholders an improved understanding of these dynamics, including why an innovation is successful or not.

The primary end-users of the tool are water managers and other practitioners at the basin or catchment levels. By applying the tool, they can identify the strengths and weaknesses of their current water management practices and focus improving the practices to the most relevant issues. Thus, the tool is not targeted, for example to lay members of the public or academics. Stakeholders with responsibility or decision-making power at the national level, such as policy officials from ministries, can provide broader insights and are encouraged to be also engaged when applying the tool. Considering the varying local contexts at the basin or catchment level, the assessment criteria and indicators can be further tailored for practical use, while still building on existing assessment approaches.

A basic way of using the tool is to apply it first at the start of the governance innovation to assess the current state of the governance regime. With this ex-ante assessment, **the user** can diagnose the relevant and urgent issues to be improved in the current regime and set ambitions to **improve** them. The second application of the tool is carried out ex-post, i.e., after the implementation of the innovation to analyse whether any positive change has been achieved in the governance regime. However, there are also other ways of applying to tool (e.g. to compare various regimes by assessing them and analysing the reasoning behind the differences), and the use of the tool should be adapted to meet the needs of the case.

4.1. Design Process of the Tool

The design process of the tool consisted of five steps, as summarised in Table 1 and elaborated below.

Table 1. Overview of the co-design process of the GOVAQUA assessment tool

Step	What?	Who?	When?
1	Design of the questions for baseline description	WP1 team with input from all GOVAQUA partners and reflections from EAB members	September 2023-April 2024
2	Design of the criteria and indicator set	WP1 team with input from all GOVAQUA partners and reflections from EAB members	September 2023-April 2024
3	Design of the scoring method	WP1 team with input from all GOVAQUA partners and reflections from EAB members	September 2023-April 2024
4	First version of the tool and testing of it	WP1 team and Living Labs	April-May 2024
5	Second version of the tool	WP1 team	June 2024

Step 1. Design of the questions for baseline description of the governance regime

The first task when applying the tool is to describe the baseline for the current governance regime and for the governance innovations that are co-created and tested in the Living Lab. This relates to understanding and benchmarking the current water governance setting, which is also the first of three tasks within the Living Lab Exploration phase (cf. Living Lab Process Design (Sojamo et al., 2023)).

For the baseline description, the tool has a set of questions to be answered by the user. If desired, external stakeholders can be involved in answering these questions, for instance through workshops or expert interviews. The first set of questions was drafted by the WP1 team based on the GAT presented in section 2.2. The GAT has been developed to describe and assess the governance regime relevant to the implementation of policy measures, strategies or projects. It conceptualizes a governance regime using **five dimensions** (presented here in the order that is recommended): 1) **problem perspectives and ambitions**, 2) **strategies and instruments**, 3) **levels and scales**, 4) **actors and networks**, and 5) **resources and responsibilities**. For each dimension, we developed two series of questions:

- **Descriptive questions** that provide a description of the governance regime;
- **Assessment questions** that focus on whether dimensions are supported or not and, hence, what perhaps can or should be improved to enable successful implementation.

The draft set of questions was discussed in the expert workshop that took place on 14 March 2024 during the consortium meeting in Malaga, Spain, with the participation of representatives from all project partners, including representatives from the six Living Labs, and three members of the External Advisory Board (a detailed workshop report was submitted on 4 June 2024 as project Milestone #1). Based on the feedback, the set of questions was revised by the WP1 team, and finalised as presented in Table 3.

Step 2. Design of the criteria and indicator set

The core of the tool is the assessment of the state of the governance regime now and after introducing certain innovations against relevant criteria and indicators. Similarly to the baseline description, the set of criteria and indicators for the tool was co-designed with contributions from all GOVAQUA partners and the External Advisory Board. Four key perspectives contributed to the co-design: 1) **review of existing approaches** as presented in Chapter 2; 2) **identification of relevant policy targets** identified as presented in Chapter 3; 3) discussions and reflections that took place during several **online project meetings**; and 4) **expert workshop** at the consortium meeting in Malaga, Spain.

The design process proceeded as follows: Considering the reviewed assessment approaches and the objectives of GOVAQUA, the WP1 team first proposed a draft list of criteria and indicators. Project partners provided feedback to these elements via several online meetings. The set of criteria and indicators was discussed during the expert workshop using four questions as the basis for input and reflection:

1. What is your overall opinion about the composition of the dimensions, criteria and indicators?
2. Are there any indicators that you wouldn't be able to assess for your Living Lab? Why?
3. What are the indicators that might not be relevant for your Living Lab? Why?
4. Are there any important criteria and/or indicators that you don't see in the current set?

During these discussions, participants reflected on the criteria and indicators, which were then adjusted accordingly by revising, merging, or removing the existing criteria or indicators, and adding new ones. In general, it was deemed important to provide definitions and examples for each criterion. It was noted that a prioritisation of the criteria depending on the Living Lab context could prove useful in order not to overburden the stakeholders applying the tool. The indicators about justice were seen as particularly useful. It was also emphasised that the wording should be shifted from a conceptual to an applied, practice-oriented tone. Participants also noted that subjective responses can be avoided by providing multiple perspectives to the questions answered in the tool.

When developing the indicators, we paid attention to the four **principles** of good indicators: credibility, salience, legitimacy and feasibility (see Figure 3). These principles apply to a single indicator at a time. Besides these indicator-wise principles, it is also important to ensure that the selected set of indicators as a

whole satisfies certain principles, such as avoiding overlaps between indicators, compactness of the set, and covering all the important issues. For further discussion about principles for selecting a good set of indicators, see Niemeijer and De Groot (2008) or Pires et al. (2020). The pertinence of these principles from the viewpoint of GOVAQUA was also discussed during the expert workshop. In general, the principles of **relevance** (“F” in Figure 3, part of salience) and **understandability** (“I” in Figure 3, at the interface of legitimacy and salience) were considered to cover quite much of the needs for indicators, and from the practical viewpoint, **scalability and transferability** (“G” in Figure 3, part of salience) were also seen as pertinent. Almost all the principles were considered to be relevant at least in some way. However, the role of **wide acceptability** (“L” in Figure 3, at the interface of legitimacy and salience) was questioned, as an indicator can be good even if it is not widely accepted. On the other hand, acceptability is partly related to stakeholder commitment, which is crucial. It was also discussed whether the indicator set of GOVAQUA meets these principles, and in general the set was seen quite comprehensively to cover all the important issues and to be in line with these principles.

Figure 3. Principles for selecting good indicators (Source: van Oudenhoven et al., 2018)

Based on all the input that partners have provided online and in the expert workshop, the WP1 team developed the list of indicators for the first version of the tool. This list is presented in detail in section 4.2.

Step 3. Design of the scoring method

The selection of the scoring method is important in terms of providing a desired level of accuracy for the assessment. The process of designing the scoring method was carried out alongside the design of the indicator set. As a basis for discussions, the WP1 team reviewed assessment approaches introduced in Chapter 2, which offer different options for scoring the criteria and indicators, as summarised in Table 2. The four scoring schemes in Table 2 were discussed during the expert workshop by answering the following questions:

- What are the advantages and disadvantages of the above scoring methods?
- Which scoring methods fit the best for the GOVAQUA assessment tool and why?
- Do you know other scoring methods that can be used for the GOVAQUA assessment tool?

Table 2. Scoring schemes that are used in the reviewed approaches

Approach	Composition	Scoring method	Re-assessment over time	Reference
OECD indicator framework and self-assessment toolkit	12 principles; 3 indicators each (what, who, how?) and 36 measures	1) in place, functioning 2) in place, partly implemented 3) in place, not implemented 4) framework under development 5) not in place 6) not applicable	Advice to re-assess within three years - Improvement - Stable - Decrease	OECD (2018)
WSC Index of UWTF	7 goals; 34 indicators	Scores from 1 to 5 for each indicators, unique score descriptions	None	Chesterfield et al. (2016)
CATCH self-assessment tool	3 WSC pillars; 22 indicators and 22 scorings	Scores from 1 to 6 for each indicator; unique score descriptions; colour codes according to 6 WSC stages	Quantitative changes in scoring from baseline to future assessments	Özerol et al. (2020)
GAT practitioners' version	5 governance dimensions; 4 quality criteria and 20 questions	Standard answers that correspond to five situations: 1) supportive 2) neutral 3) restrictive 4) not known 5) not relevant	Trends can be identified in terms of upward, downward or no change	Özerol and Bressers (2023)

While the participants were not fully familiar with the tools and their scoring schemes, their opinions provided a different perspective to the one that researchers who have worked with those tools might have:

- Regarding the OECD framework, the participants acknowledged its qualitative approach and mentioned that comparing countries with such a framework is difficult. Still, among its advantages are its comprehensiveness and the fact that its application requires input from stakeholders. Among the criticisms was that its application can be intensive, requiring a lot of resources.
- For the WSC Index, the participants highlighted that due to GOVAQUA's diverse objectives, it might be difficult to have only one tool, but principles could be a starting point. In general, the participants liked the types of goals and indicators but confirmed that transparency is needed to understand how the indicators are scored.
- For the CATCH self-assessment, the participants did not provide comments, as they mentioned a lack of familiarity.
- Regarding the GAT, they highlighted that it is academic and welcomed the translation of the tool to a practice-oriented one. Still, they wondered how easy it is to conduct the assessment for those applying the tool. In this regard, a suggestion was to make the scoring method as simple as possible.

The participants highlighted the importance of an adequate scoring method, as the desired level of depth for the responses remains unclear. However, the participants had issues selecting one tool among the four for developing GOVAQUA indicators. They highlighted that the pool of indicators provided by the four tools should be sufficient to find the ones required for GOVAQUA. They suggested applying “reverse engineering” to select the methods and indicators, being mindful of the time frame when looking at the evaluation of the progress. Ultimately, the scoring method should contain what we want to achieve, and the starting point can be the principles that the innovations aim to achieve.

Reflecting on the discussions, the project team decided to adopt a **four-point scale**, with potential **scores from 1 to 4 for all indicators** and two additional scores to address the situations where there is **insufficient data** to score the indicator, or the indicator is **not relevant** for the given Living Lab. This scoring method was expected to offer adequate differentiation of the status in each indicator, while also avoiding the ‘middle point bias’. For cases where a more detailed scoring scheme is needed, Box 2 provides an example of one such scheme for assessing the criterion “Ensure good water sensitive governance” with indicator “Water is key element in city planning and design”.

Box 2. Example indicator scoring description (Chesterfield et al., 2016)

1: Water policy and management beyond essential services are rarely considered in matters of urban planning.

2: General policy on sustainability is in place but there is a lack of focus on integrated water system planning.

3: Urban water policy acknowledges the role of integrated water management planning and water system planning coordination between organisations occurs, often led by a single agency or department.

4: Urban water policy acknowledges the role of integrated water management planning and some collaboration between organisations occurs. Contingency planning are routinely used and incorporate methods such as scenario planning to deal with uncertainty around issues such as population growth and climate change. Monitoring and evaluation of planning is in place.

5: Water system planning is fully integrated in urban planning and design. Cross-sectoral collaboration to water system planning is mandated in official policy and included in statutory planning frameworks. Contingency planning are routinely used and incorporate methods such as scenario planning, robust decision making and exploratory modelling to deal with uncertainty around issues such as population growth and climate change. Monitoring and evaluation of planning is in place. Urban design guidelines address the critical role of water in achieving liveability, sustainability, resilience and productivity goals. Strategies and plans are explicitly adaptive.

One conclusion of the feedback from the expert workshop was that (un)sustainable and/or (un)equitable water use can differ based on the context. Therefore, a detailed scoring method could be prepared, including a description for each score of each indicator. This method has not been adopted as it would require ample efforts, which might not prove useful for users due to differences in local contexts or language barriers.

Step 4. First version of the assessment tool and testing of it

Based on the analysis and discussions in steps 1-3, the WP1 team developed the first version (v1) of the assessment tool in March-April 2024. It consists of the questionnaire for assessing the baseline description, as well as the criteria and indicators for assessing how the governance regime at the catchment/basin level supports or hinders the water governance innovations (Section 4.2.2) with the developed scale (Section 4.2.3). Based on the discussions during online meetings and the expert workshop, guidance on how to apply the tool was prepared as presented in Appendices C and D, and standard templates were provided for Living Lab partners to test the tool by conducting the baseline description and indicator scoring.

The v1 was tested in April-May 2024 by the Living Labs. Testing the tool served three purposes: 1) improving the applicability of the tool in terms of being simple, tailored and complete; 2) assessing the current status of governance to set ambitions for transitioning to sustainable and equitable water use, and to inform the choice of tested innovation in focus; and 3) drawing lessons from the tool application to provide effective guidance for future users of the tool. During this period, three online meetings were held to discuss the progress of the Living Labs with the testing of the tool and to resolve possible issues that arose during testing.

After the Living Labs tested the v1, the WP1 team analysed their feedback and the application results. The objectives of this analysis were twofold. First, the set of criteria and indicators and the scoring method were finalised using the feedback from the Living Labs based on their first application. Second, the initial assessment results were analysed as illustrative examples of how the governance regimes support or hinder the design and implementation of water governance innovations.

Step 5. Second version of the assessment tool

Based on the feedback and results from the application of v1 by the Living Labs, the WP1 team developed the second version of the assessment tool (v2). Furthermore, the guidance for applying the tool was revised according to the experience of the Living Labs and expert workshop discussions. The baseline description questions, and the indicator set and scoring table were prepared in the form of an Excel file. Further guidance is provided in the appendices C and D of this deliverable regarding the application of the tool.

4.2. Content of the Tool

4.2.1 Baseline Description of the Governance Regime

Table 3 presents the set of questions for the baseline description of the governance regime. Depending on the objectives and needs of the user, the baseline description may focus only on Part A: Descriptive questions or also incorporate Part B: Assessment questions (see Appendix C for further guidance on conducting the baseline description). The questions are aimed to be answered first by the GOVAQUA Living Labs and also the future users of the tool to a) understand the water governance challenges and problems to be addressed, b) if they are already known, consider them from the perspective of the specific governance innovation in focus. In the Living Labs, the innovations are generally co-created (i.e., developed in collaboration with various stakeholders) and tested (i.e., implemented for the first time and evaluated).

Table 3. Questions to develop the baseline by describing the governance regime
(Source: GAT adapted from Bressers et al., 2013)

Dimension	Part A: Descriptive questions	Part B: Assessment questions
Problem perspectives and goal ambitions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the key water management and governance problems in the area? If already selected, which water management and governance problem does the innovation in question address? How urgent are these problems to stakeholders? 2. What are the public perceptions regarding the problem? What is the level of public awareness? 3. What goals are set in the relevant policy documents and political statements in relation to the problem? 4. Have any of the problem perspectives or goals changed over time or are likely to change in the future? 	21. Is any important problem perspective missing or overlooked in the context that should be considered in the Living Lab?
Strategies and instruments*	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. Which strategies or policy instruments are already in place to address the problem at hand? If known, which strategies or instruments does the innovation adopt? 6. Which other strategies or policy instruments could be applied to solve the problem addressed by the innovation? 7. Have any of the strategies or instruments changed over time or are likely to change in the future? 	22. Are there any key strategies or policy instruments missing or overlooked in the context that should be considered in the Living Lab?
Levels and scales	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Which administrative levels (municipality, county, province, state, etc.) are involved in solving the problem, and if known, co-creating and testing of the innovation? 9. Which hydrological level (catchment or sub catchment) is relevant for the problem, and if known, for the innovation, and in what way? 10. Are there any mismatches between the administrative and hydrological regions that complicate solving the problem, or if known, applying the innovation? 11. Have any of the levels changed over time or are likely to change in the future? 	23. Are any relevant levels missing or overlooked in the context that should be considered in the Living Lab?
Actors and networks	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 12. Which actors are involved in solving the problem, or if known, co-creating and testing the innovation and in what role? What network relationships do they have within or outside the problem frame and what type of interactions take place between the actors? 13. Which actors are only involved as affected by or beneficiaries of the problem solving, or if known, the innovation? 14. Have any of the actors or networks changed over time or are likely to change in the future? 	<p>24. Are any relevant stakeholders missing or overlooked in the context that should be included in the Living Lab?</p> <p>25. Do relevant external networks support the innovation?</p>

Dimension	Part A: Descriptive questions	Part B: Assessment questions
Responsibilities and resources	<p>15. Which organization(s) have the responsibility to implement solutions to solve the problem, or if known, implement the innovation? What kind of legal mandate does the organization have?</p> <p>16. What resources (legal authority, funding, personnel, expertise, etc.) do responsible organisations have to fulfil their tasks?</p> <p>17. What is the scope of knowledge base that is available and accessible on the water system at the catchment level?</p> <p>18. Have any of the responsibilities or resources changed over time or are likely to change in the future?</p>	<p>26. Do the organizations responsible for the innovation have the resources for implementation?</p> <p>27. Is the innovation supported by resources that ensure transparency and monitoring?</p> <p>28. Is the knowledge base sufficient and used in an efficient way?</p>

* Strategies refer to the policy style for public intervention or decision-making (Bressers and Kuks, 2013). Meanwhile, instruments can be understood as the tools, approaches or techniques used to achieve a policy objective, which refers here to sustainable and equitable water use (See also Box 1).

Box 1. Types of policy instruments (adapted from Kaufman et al., 2001)

Regulatory instruments (also referred to as command and control) is about enforcement by means of law and regulation, e.g. water licenses, zoning.

Economic instruments are about influencing costs, benefits or markets, e.g. water abstraction charges, compensation for crop losses or establishment of water markets.

Information and communication instruments are about providing information in the form of, for example, facts, options or norms and communication e.g. data portals, mass media.

Collaborative instruments focus on reaching public-private agreements and the development of certification or labels, e.g. water stewardship initiatives.

Service and infrastructure instruments focus on allowing or enabling others to take desirable action or hindering or inhibiting undesirable action (removing an option).

4.2.2 Assessment Criteria and Indicators

Table 4 presents the set of assessment criteria and indicators applied in the tool. Within the context of GOVAQUA, the two underlying fundamentals of water governance are **sustainability** and **equity** (cf. Chapter 1). Through the assessment tool, these are translated into **9 criteria** that are assessed using **32 indicators**.

The five governance dimensions used for the baseline description form the basis for the assessment of the criteria and indicators. The reasoning behind this dual approach (i.e., first a baseline description and then an assessment), is the premise that the dimensions of the governance regime should be first described, including its main problems, strategies, levels, actors, resources, etc., before assessing the regime based on multiple criteria and indicators, which relate to one or more of the governance dimensions. For instance, the dimension “Problem perspectives and goal ambitions” is obviously linked to the criterion “State of the freshwater environment”, whereas it can also be linked to multiple indicators of policy goals, which are relevant for the criteria on coordination and policy mixes. Due to the inherent multiplicity of the interlinkages among the governance dimensions and the assessment criteria and indicators, there has been no attention to specifying the linkages.

The criteria and indicators focus on the catchment/basin level and **how the governance regime at the catchment/basin level supports or hinders the innovations that are developed in the Living Labs**, also acknowledging that the regime frameworks and key actors may also stem from or operate at the national level. In contrast, **WPs 2-5 in GOVAQUA analyse and/or assess specific governance innovations** at multiple levels, as do the Living Labs as well.

It should be noted that not all the assessment criteria focus on the same group of actors. For the justice-related criteria, a differentiation is made between water users (as both individuals and divided into different demographic, social and economic groups) and organised stakeholders (water user organisations, governmental and non-governmental organisations, private companies, professional organisations, academia, etc.), depending on the focus of specific indicators. For the institutional capacity and horizontal and vertical coordination criteria, the focus is on organised stakeholders, namely public sector, civil society, and the private sector.

Table 4. The set of assessment criteria and indicators

Criteria	Indicator titles
1. State of the freshwater environment	1.1. Achievement of relevant policy requirements
2. Fair sharing of data and information	2.1. Completeness of available water data and information 2.2. Accuracy of available water data and information 2.3. Access to water data and information 2.4. Effectiveness of water information sharing
3. Distributional justice	3.1. Allocation of water resources among users 3.2. Access of population to safe water and sanitation 3.3. Distribution of benefits from water access among users 3.4. Distribution of costs from water access among users 3.5. Distribution of harmful impacts among users 3.6. Exposure and preparedness to water-related climate hazards
4. Recognitional justice	4.1. Recognition of different water users and their needs 4.2. Balance among the values and roles of water users
5. Procedural justice	5.1. Representation of water users and stakeholders 5.2. Participatory mechanisms to involve water users and stakeholders 5.3. Representation of different types of knowledge 5.4. Involvement of water users in vulnerable conditions 5.5. Transparency of decision-making processes in the water sector 5.6. Accountability of the decision-makers of the water sector
6. Financial efficiency and effectiveness	6.1. Economic value of water investments 6.2. Non-economic values of water investments 6.3. Financing available for different water uses
7. Institutional capacity	7.1. Resources and capacity of stakeholders in water governance 7.2. Leadership of responsible organisations in water governance 7.3. Ownership of water-related problems by different stakeholders
8. Horizontal and vertical coordination	8.1. Coordination among organisations in water-using sectors 8.2. Coordination among multiple levels of water governance 8.3. Fit between administrative and hydrological levels 8.4. Consideration of external actors and factors in water governance
9. Enabling policy mix	9.1. Completeness of policy instruments 9.2. Effectiveness of policy instruments 9.3. Coherence among the policy instruments

Appendix E provides the detailed questions for assessing the indicators and the possible scores for each indicator. The order in which the criteria and indicators are applied does not have to follow the order presented in Table 4 and can be tailored to the user's needs.

4.2.3 Scoring Method

The assessment tool (v2) applies the **four-point scale** with the following potential generic **scores from 1 to 4 for all indicators**:

- 1 = an extremely negative judgement that implies a fully undesired level for sustainability and/or equity.
- 2 = a negative judgement that implies an undesired level for sustainability and/or equity, with ample room for improvement.
- 3 = a positive judgment that implies a desired level for sustainability and/or equity, with room for improvement.
- 4 = an extremely positive judgment that implies a fully desired level for sustainability and equity that should be preserved.

As presented in Appendix E, the descriptions for scores 1 and 4 are provided for each indicator, whereas no descriptions are provided for scores 2 and 3. This choice has been made to allow for simplicity during the scoring process. The user can select the score 2 if the status is not fully undesired, but also not at a desired level. Similarly, the score 3 can be select if the status is at a desired level, while there is still room for improvement. Overall, the scoring method doesn't aim to quantify the assessment results, but rather show the status and potential for transitioning towards a full desired level of sustainability and equity.

The political and institutional context, within which the governance innovations take place, varies significantly across river basins in Europe. Thus, no specific descriptions are provided for each indicator score. Based on the discussions with and feedback from the Living Lab partners and other project team members, the scoring scheme is deemed flexible enough to reflect the variety in local contexts and concrete enough to differentiate what is being assessed with different types of indicators. At the same time, scoring is only one aspect of the assessment. It is essential to substantiate the scores and also reflect on the specifics of the local context that need further attention. To address these issues, the tool incorporates two measures, as shown in the last four columns of Appendix E. First, in addition to the four scores, options of **insufficient data** and **not relevant** can be used to assess the indicator by answering the respective questions. The "insufficient data" option allows the users to reflect the data availability conditions in their basin/catchment, whereas the "not relevant" option offers the flexibility to exclude the indicators that do not fit the local context of the governance innovation that is being tested. Second, for each indicator, the users are encouraged to substantiate the chosen scores (or not giving a score) by proving a brief explanation of their reasoning.

4.3. Application of the Tool in the Living Labs

The application process of the tool in GOVAQUA Living Labs consists of three steps, as shown in Table 5 and elaborated below.

Table 5. Overview of the application process of the GOVAQUA assessment tool

Step	What?	Who?	When?
1	Testing of the tool (version 1)	All the Living Lab partners. For Finland, France, Spain: Selected external stakeholders	April-May 2024
2	First application of the tool (version 2)	All the Living Lab partners and their external stakeholders	September-October 2024
3	Second application of the tool	All the Living Lab partners and their external stakeholders	2026

Step 1. Testing of the tool (version 1)

In April-May 2024, all the Living Labs provided feedback to the v1 of the tool. The Living Lab partners in France, Finland, Spain and the UK answered the baseline description questions, and the Living Lab partners in France and Finland also assessed the indicators internally, without conducting a stakeholder workshop. The results from these initial descriptions and assessments are presented in chapter 5.

Additionally, the Living Lab partners in Finland, France and Spain discussed the baseline description and the indicator set with selected external stakeholders. These discussions enabled the external stakeholders, who are among the first applicants of the tool, to contribute to both assessing their governance regime and also participating in the tool development process. Such stakeholders act as a “sounding board” to test whether the indicator set and scoring method makes sense, without the need to decide which scores to give to which indicator. Therefore, having selected a few trusted stakeholders in this step is crucial for the Living Lab partners.

Step 2. First application of the tool (version 2)

For all the Living Labs, the full application of the assessment tool is planned to take place in September-October 2024 as part of the Exploration phase. They will apply the v2 of the tool. Based on the assessment results they will identify their level of achievement for each indicator. They will also set ambitions to improve their governance regime through the implementation of the innovation in their Living Lab. For indicators that are assessed to be at a (fully) undesired level, ambitions should be set to prioritise the sustainability and/or equity issues related to the indicator. For indicators that with a (full) desired level, they set ambitions to improve or protect their status.

Considering that there are multiple indicators under each criterion (except criterion 1), it is likely that for the same criterion, the scores can be low for some indicators and high for others. There are too many such possible outcomes to account for, and the GOVAQUA assessment tool prioritises the value of considering multiple aspects of the regime over the quantification of assessment results. Therefore, we haven't included a step for the aggregation of the assessment results from the indicator level to the criterion level, nor from the criterion level to the regime level.

If deemed essential, the users can consider the relative importance, or the weight, of the indicators to aggregate the results from the indicator level to the criterion level. In such a case, answering the following questions for their situation would guide the users in choosing the aggregated score: Can a high score in most of the indicators compensate for a low score in one high-weight indicator? Could having a very low score for a high-weight indicator be interpreted as a low score for the whole criterion? Would having a very high score for a high-weight indicator be sufficient to give a high score for the whole criterion? While aggregation of the results to the criterion level might provide an overall picture, it is still valuable to set the ambitions at the indicator level, where the actions for improving the governance regime can be more concretely identified. Regarding the aggregation to the governance regime level, this is not an advisable step, as it would imply giving a single score for the whole governance regime. Such a score lacks added-value for improving the decision-making processes and oversimplifies the complexity of the regime.

A suggested approach for the GOVAQUA Living Labs is to organise a workshop for external stakeholders so that they can contribute to the assessment of indicators. For the Living Labs that plan to invite the external stakeholders only for the application of the tool in September-October 2024, it is essential to share information about the tool prior to the stakeholder workshop.

Step 3. Second application of the assessment tool

In 2026, the Living Labs will apply the assessment tool for a second time during their Evaluation and Feedback phase. They will assess their governance regime again; compare it with the status from the first application; and if needed, reconsider their initial ambitions. Regarding a possible aggregation of results from the indicator level to the criterion level, it is recommended to follow the same approach during both the first and the second application of the tool.

During the two-year period between the two applications, it is likely that only minor changes occur in the governance regime and the development of the innovation remains limited to designing and testing it with stakeholders. Therefore, the second application can be broader in scope, including both the assessment of indicators, and involving stakeholders to reflect on the governance enablers and barriers based on the lessons learned for improving the governance conditions in that regime. The GOVAQUA project team will also organise a workshop involving all Living Labs and their stakeholders to discuss the assessment results from the second application.

5. Results from the First Application of the Assessment Tool

This chapter summarises the results of the first application of the tool, i.e. the baseline description and the indicator scoring. All GOVAQUA Living Labs are planning to conduct a full application of the assessment tool in September-October 2024. Therefore, these results here should be seen more as illustrative examples of the insights that can be gained by applying the tool, rather than final results.

5.1. Baseline Descriptions

Partners in four Living Labs (France, Finland, Spain and the UK) carried out an initial description of their governance baseline, with varying levels of depth and some questions left unanswered due to a lack of data. We summarise the main observations from these descriptions below.

Problem perspectives and goal ambitions: The four Living Labs vary in terms of water management and governance problems, with competition among water users and water quality issues being the two main overarching issues. For each Living Lab, multiple policy targets are seen as relevant, some at the regional level and others at the national or EU levels.

Strategies and instruments: A diverse set of strategies and instruments are in place in different Living Labs, covering regulatory, economic as well as information, communication, or digital instruments. At the same time, new instruments are expected to be introduced in some countries. In some of the Living Labs, partners already have a clear idea how their innovation interacts with both existing strategies and instruments as well as the new ones or the changes that can be expected.

Levels and scales: For most of the Living Labs, the partners have identified the main organisations that function at different levels. Yet, the multi-level governance structure is not fully clear in all cases. Partners also have a clear understanding of the hydrological units and the interactions with administrative levels that can affect the implementation of the innovation.

Actors and networks: The broad set of actors and their roles are known to all the Living Lab partners. Yet, most of them haven't mapped the actor interactions and networks or find it beyond their needs to understand the interactions. In some Living Labs, changes in actor networks or of the organisational structure of specific actors are expected to have implications.

Responsibilities and resources: Partners in some Living Labs have a good understanding of the responsibilities and resources of different actors, while others have yet to identify these.

Regarding the assessment questions that are included in the baseline description (Part B questions), some of these proved to be difficult for the Living Lab partners. They stated that they need more data to answer them or more time, as they first need to define their innovation more concretely.

5.2. Indicator Scoring

The Living Lab lead partner in France provided a full list of indicator scores. In addition, the Living Lab lead partner in Finland provided scores for the indicators under the first three criteria. As the scores are too limited to draw any conclusions, we provide here only two key observations. The first observation is regarding the indicators that the Living Labs found difficult to understand. Second is regarding the indicators that Living Lab partners did not have sufficient data about for assessment.

Most of the indicators that the Living Lab partners found difficult to understand are related to the categorisation of individuals or organisations, such as water users, community groups and stakeholders. Another type of confusion resulted from the definition of the four-point scale for some indicators, such as the use of "desired level" in the scale. To clarify such issues, we provided explanations and examples in section 4.2.2 and Appendix E. Regarding the indicators, for which the Living Lab partners did not have sufficient data, the issue often resulted from lack of clarity on what was being assessed by the indicator. For such indicators, we revised the title of the indicator, the question to assess the indicator, or both.

5.2. Dissemination of the Tool and Assessment Results

After the full application of the tool, we plan to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the assessment results and make further adjustments to the tool based on the user feedback. Both the tool itself and the results from its initial applications will be disseminated to wider audiences. We will publish on the project website both this report as well as a summary of the tool elements, a guidance document for tool application, and the Excel file which can be used for the baseline description and for scoring of the indicators. As part of WP6, the GOVAQUA Living Labs have started applying the tool and will include in their final report (Deliverable 6.9) additional reflection and experiences of the tool application. Before the end of the project, we will also publish the tool and its guidance documents on the GOVAQUA Online Academy (Deliverable 7.2) for future end-users. Finally, based on the tool application results, we (WP1 and WP6 team members) plan to write a scientific manuscript to disseminate the tool and empirical results to scientific audiences.

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Appendix A. Elements of Existing Assessment Approaches

Figure A1. OECD Water Governance Principles (Source: OECD, 2015)

Table A1. Descriptive questions of the GAT (Source: Bressers et al., 2013)

Governance dimension	Questions
Levels and scales	Which administrative levels are involved and how? Which hydrological scales are considered and in what way? To what extent do they depend on each other or act productively on their own? Have any of these changed over time or are likely to change in the foreseeable future?
Actors and networks	Which actors are involved in the process? What are their roles? To what extent do they have network relationships also outside of the case under study? Which actors are only involved as affected by or beneficiaries of the measures taken? What are the conflicts between these stakeholders? What forms of dialogue take place between them? Are there actors with a mediating role? Have any of these changed over time or are likely to change in the foreseeable future?
Problem perspectives and goal ambitions	Which various angles does the debate of public and stakeholders take towards the problem at hand? What levels of possible disturbance are current policies designed to cope with? What levels of disturbance of normal water use are deemed acceptable by different stakeholders? What goals are stipulated in the relevant policy white papers and political statements? Have any of these changed over time or are likely to change in the foreseeable future?
Strategies and instruments	Which policy instruments and measures are used to modify the problem situation? To what extent do they reflect a certain strategy of influence (regulative, incentive, communicative, technical etc.)? Have any of these changed over time or are likely to change in the foreseeable future?
Responsibilities and resources	Which organisations have responsibility for what tasks under the relevant policies and customs? What legal authorities and other resources are given to them for this purpose, or do they possess inherently? What transparencies are demanded and monitored regarding their use? Is there sufficient knowledge on the water system available? Have any of these changed over time or are likely to change in the foreseeable future?

Table A2. Water governance assessment matrix (Source: Casiano et al., 2019)

Dimensions	Criteria			
	Extent	Coherence	Flexibility	Intensity
Levels and scales	How many levels are involved and dealing with an issue? Are there any important gaps or missing levels?	Do the levels work together, and do they trust each other between levels? To what degree is the mutual dependence recognised?	Is it possible to move up and down levels (upscaling and downscaling) given the issue at stake?	Is there a strong impact from a certain level towards behavioural change or management reform?
Actors and networks	Are all relevant stakeholders involved? Who are excluded?	What is the strength of interactions among stakeholders? How are these interactions institutionalised? Do the stakeholders have collaboration experience? Do they trust and respect each other?	Is it possible to include new actors or shift from one actor to another if there are pragmatic reasons for this? Do the actors share social capital allowing them to support each other's task?	Is there a strong impact from an actor or actor coalition towards behavioural change or management reform?
Problem perspectives and goal ambitions	To what extent are the various problem perspectives taken into account?	To what extent do the various goals support each other, or are they in competition or conflict?	Are there opportunities to re-assess goals?	How different are the goal ambitions from the status quo?
Strategies and instruments	What types of instruments are included in the strategy and implemented, and which are excluded?	Is the resulting incentive system based on synergy? Are there any overlaps or conflicts of incentives created by the included policy instruments?	Are there opportunities to combine or make use of different types of instruments? Is there a choice?	What is the implied behavioural deviation from current practice and how strongly do the instruments require and enforce this?
Responsibilities and resources	Are responsibilities clearly assigned and sufficiently facilitated with resources?	Do the assigned responsibilities create competence struggles or cooperation within or across institutions?	Is it possible to pool the responsibilities and resources as long as accountability and transparency are not compromised?	Are the allocated resources sufficient to implement the measures needed for the intended change?

Figure A2. Conceptual framework of analysis (Source: Pahl-Wostl et al., 2020)

Figure A3. Conceptual framework of analysis with all variables (Source: Pahl-Wostl et al., 2020)

Figure A4. Generic template of an Action Situation (Source: Pahl-Wostl et al., 2020)

Table A3. Types of action situation that relate to governance functions (Source: Pahl-Wostl et al., 2020)

Functions	Definition and explanation
Rule Making	Social interactions that have some kind of rules as a product.
Knowledge Generation	Social interactions that have knowledge of relevance for other governance functions and possibly also for operational activities – provision of ecosystem services as a product.
Conflict Resolution	Social interactions that are specifically designed to resolve conflicts. These could for example be legal procedures or round tables.
Coordination	Social interactions that are specifically designed to support the coordinated development and implementation of strategies, plans, activities etc. These could be an instrument that links spatial planning and water management, or a payment for ecosystem services scheme that links two sectors (e.g. water and agriculture). Such instruments should follow a specified process and have clearly identifiable products (e.g. cooperation agreements).
Enforcement of Rules	Procedures in place to ensure compliance with rules. This may involve monitoring the achievement of pre-defined goals, environmental targets etc. as well as procedures that assess the compliance with rules and their enforcement (e.g. sanctions).
Planning	Social interactions that have some kind of plans as a product (strategic plans, operational water management plans etc.).
Application of Measures	The application of specific measures or programmes. Outputs are not plans but more tangible products (e.g. payment schemes or a new governmental authority).

Table A4. The goals and indicators of the WSC Index (Source: Chesterfield et al., 2016)

Goal 1. Ensure good water sensitive governance	1.1 Knowledge, skills and organisational capacity 1.2 Water is key element in city planning and design 1.3 Cross-sector institutional arrangements and processes 1.4 Public engagement, participation and transparency 1.5 Leadership, long-term vision and commitment 1.6 Water resourcing and funding to deliver broad societal value 1.7 Equitable representation of perspectives
Goal 2. Increase community capital	2.1 Water literacy 2.2 Connection with water 2.3 Shared ownership, management and responsibility 2.4 Community preparedness and response to extreme events 2.5 Indigenous involvement in water planning
Goal 3. Achieve equity of essential services	3.1 Equitable access to safe and secure water supply 3.2 Equitable access to safe and reliable sanitation 3.3 Equitable access to flood protection 3.4 Equitable and affordable access to amenity values of water-related assets
Goal 4. Improve productivity & resource efficiency	4.1 Maximised resource recovery 4.2 Low GHG emission in water sector 4.3 Water-related business opportunities 4.4 Low end-user potable water demand 4.5 Benefits across other sectors
Goal 5. Improve ecological health	5.1 Healthy and biodiverse habitat 5.2 Surface water quality and flows 5.3 Groundwater quality and replenishment 5.4 Protect existing areas of high ecological value
Goal 6. Ensure quality urban space	6.1 Activating connected green - blue space 6.2 Urban elements functioning to mitigate heat impacts 6.3 Vegetation coverage
Goal 7. Promote adaptive infrastructure	7.1 Diversify self-sufficient fit-for-purpose water supply 7.2 Multi-functional water infrastructure 7.3 Integration and intelligent control 7.4 Robust infrastructure 7.5 Infrastructure and ownership at multiple scales 7.6 Adequate maintenance

Table A5. WSC index tailored to midsize cities in the North Sea Region (Source: Özerol et al., 2020)

WSC pillars	Cities as Water Sensitive Communities	Cities as Water Catchments	Cities as Providers of Ecosystem Services
Indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organizational capacity at the city level • Water as a key element in city planning and design/redesign • City-level integrative arrangements across sectors • Stakeholder participation in water and climate adaptation • Leadership, long-term vision and commitment by city administration • Level of flood risk awareness of the population • Organisation of emergency management • Regulations to reduce potential flood damage in the city 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability and use of flood hazard and flood risk maps for areas at risk • Areas to temporarily store water in the city without expected damage • Measures to increase infiltration • Status of infrastructure for water supply • Maintenance of infrastructure for water supply • Status of infrastructure for wastewater • Maintenance of infrastructure for wastewater • Status of infrastructure for flood protection • Maintenance of infrastructure for flood protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attention to the needs and protection of vulnerable groups against the negative impacts of climate change • Healthy and biodiverse habitat • Protection of surface water quality and flow regime • Protection of groundwater quality and groundwater levels • Activation of connected urban green and blue space • Vegetation coverage at the city level

Appendix B. SDG6 Targets and Indicators

Table B1. Targets and indicators for the SDG 6 “Clean water and sanitation” and their relevance for the GOVAQUA project

Target	Indicator	Relevant for GOVAQUA?
6.1 By 2030, achieve universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water for all	6.1.1 Proportion of population using safely managed drinking water services	No
6.2 By 2030, achieve access to adequate and equitable sanitation and hygiene for all and end open defecation, paying special attention to the needs of women and girls and those in vulnerable situations	6.2.1 Proportion of population using (a) safely managed sanitation services and (b) a hand-washing facility with soap and water	No
6.3 By 2030, improve water quality by reducing pollution, eliminating dumping and minimizing release of hazardous chemicals and materials, halving the proportion of untreated wastewater and substantially increasing recycling and safe reuse globally	6.3.1 Proportion of domestic and industrial wastewater flows safely treated	No
	6.3.2 Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality	Yes
6.4 By 2030, substantially increase water-use efficiency across all sectors and ensure sustainable withdrawals and supply of freshwater to address water scarcity and substantially reduce the number of people suffering from water scarcity	6.4.1 Change in water-use efficiency over time	No
	6.4.2 Level of water stress: freshwater withdrawal as a proportion of available freshwater resources	No
6.5 By 2030, implement integrated water resources management at all levels, including through transboundary cooperation as appropriate	6.5.1 Degree of integrated water resources management	Yes
	6.5.2 Proportion of transboundary basin area with an operational arrangement for water cooperation	No
6.6 By 2020, protect and restore water-related ecosystems, including mountains, forests, wetlands, rivers, aquifers and lakes	6.6.1 Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time	No
6.a By 2030, expand international cooperation and capacity-building support to developing countries in water- and sanitation-related activities and programmes, including water harvesting, desalination, water efficiency, wastewater treatment, recycling and reuse technologies	6.a.1 Amount of water- and sanitation-related official development assistance that is part of a government-coordinated spending plan	No
6.b Support and strengthen the participation of local communities in improving water and sanitation management	6.b.1 Proportion of local administrative units with established and operational policies and procedures for participation of local communities in water and sanitation management	Yes

Appendix C. Guidance for the Baseline Description

Application process of the baseline description

Table C1 presents the template for answering the questions about the baseline description, which is also made available in the form of an Excel file. The baseline questions can be used in multiple ways, with or without engaging other stakeholders. The most straightforward way is that the planning team fills in Part A, the descriptive part, to prepare a description of the governance context of an innovation. The team could leave it here and use this description for their own information. It is also possible to go one step further to fill in part B, the assessment part. Note that since part A provides the basis for part B, this can only be filled out after part A has been filled out.

Stakeholders could be engaged by sharing and validating the results with them in a meeting or workshop, or to even develop descriptions with stakeholders. Such stakeholder interactions could help improving the quality of the results and achieving a common understanding of an innovation and its governance context (for more information, please refer to Bressers et al, [2016](#), section 3.4, pp. 57-63).

Points of attention

Multiple descriptive questions are included for each dimension. There is no strict format to answer the questions. For instance, simply a “yes” or a “no” can be sufficient to differentiate between governance factors that are supportive vs. hindering. Each dimension also contains one descriptive question regarding changes over time (past and future). This question aims to draw attention to the dynamic nature of the governance context. For example, that changes in the past still impact the current governance context or that certain strategies or processes are forthcoming.

In the problem perspectives and goal ambitions dimension, the first question is about the problem addressed by the innovation. Here, a distinction is made between a water management problem (e.g. poor water quality, too little water) and water governance problem. Water governance refers here to “the range of political, social, economic and administrative systems that are in place to develop and manage water resources, and the delivery of water services, at different levels of society” (Rogers and Hall, 2003, p.16).

Part B of Table 3 focuses on questions that measure “extent”, i.e. what is missing or overlooked in the governance context that should be considered in the case at hand. In the original GAT, the coherence, flexibility and intensity of a governance regime are also considered as assessment criteria (see Table A2 in Appendix A). Here, the focus is on extent, as this is the most important criterion to contribute to sustainable and equitable water use.

Suggestions for the practical use of the baseline descriptions in the Living Labs

For the assessment questions, each Living Lab lead partner can decide to answer these by themselves or in collaboration with stakeholders (e.g. in a workshop). When done collaboratively, answering all questions might take significant time, which might not be readily available. Hence, it might be useful to select specific dimensions and questions and to only focus on these. It should be noted that not all stakeholders will have to assess all the dimensions. When used in a collaborative setting, there is likely to be a need to adapt certain questions to make them more understandable. Such decisions are up to the Living Lab lead partner, depending on their stakeholder network and the local context.

Ideally, an explanation should be provided for each answer so that different Living Labs can compare and learn from each other’s experiences. Nevertheless, it is up to the Living Labs in how much detail these questions are answered. The Living Lab lead partner also decides on what timeframe to consider in answering these questions.

In the strategies and instruments dimension, the Living Labs are asked to reflect on the types of policy styles as well as the tools, approaches or techniques relevant for the innovation that is being designed in the Living Lab. It is highly recommended to link the baseline description to specific policy decisions and innovations so that stakeholders can be supported in addressing urgent challenges.

Table C1. Template for the baseline description of the governance regime

Dimension	Part A: Descriptive questions	Answers (1-2 sentences each)	Part B: Assessment questions	Answers (1-2 sentences each)
Problem perspectives and goal ambitions	1. What are the key water management and governance problems in the area? If already selected, which water management and governance problem does the innovation in question address? How urgent are these problems to stakeholders?	1.	21. Is any important problem perspective missing or overlooked in the context that should be considered in the Living Lab?	21.
	2. What are the public perceptions regarding the problems? What is the level of public awareness?	2.		
	3. What relevant goals are set in the relevant policy documents and political statements in relation to the problem?	3.		
	4. Have any of the problem perspectives or goals changed over time or are likely to change in the future?	4.		
Strategies and instruments	5. Which strategies or policy instruments are already in place to address the problem at hand? If known, which strategies or instruments does the innovation adopt?	5.	22. Are there any key strategies or policy instruments missing or overlooked in the context that should be considered in the Living Lab?	22.
	6. Which other strategies or policy instruments could be applied to solve the problem that is addressed by the innovation?	6.		
	7. Have any of the other strategies or instruments changed over time or are likely to change in the future?	7.		
Levels and scales	8. Which administrative levels (municipality, county, province, state, etc.) are involved in solving the problem, and if known, co-creating and testing of the innovation?	8.	23. Are any relevant levels missing or overlooked in the context that should be considered in the Living Lab?	23.
	9. Which hydrological level (catchment or sub catchment) is relevant for the problem, and if known, for the innovation, and in what way?	9.		
		10.		

Dimension	Part A: Descriptive questions	Answers (1-2 sentences each)	Part B: Assessment questions	Answers (1-2 sentences each)	
	<p>10. Are there any mismatches between the administrative and hydrological regions that complicate solving the problem, or if known, applying the innovation?</p> <p>11. Have any of the levels changed over time or are likely to change in the future?</p>	11.			
Actors and networks	12. Which actors are involved in solving the problem, or if known, co-creating and testing the innovation and in what role? What network relationships do they have within or outside the problem frame and what type of interactions take place between the actors?	12.	24. Are any relevant stakeholders missing or overlooked in the context that should be included in the Living Lab?	24.	
	13. Which actors are only involved as affected by or beneficiaries of the problem solving, or if known, the innovation?	13.			25. Do relevant external networks support the innovation?
	14. Have any of the actors or networks changed over time or are likely to change in the future?	14.	25.		
Responsibilities and resources	15. Which organization(s) have the responsibility to implement solutions to solve the problem, or if known, implement the innovation? What kind of legal mandate does the organization have?	15.	26. Do the organizations responsible for the innovation have the resources for implementation?	26.	
	16. What resources (legal authority, funding, personnel, expertise, etc.) do responsible organisations have to fulfil their tasks?	16.			27. Is the innovation supported by resources that ensure transparency and monitoring?
	17. What is the scope of knowledge base that is available and accessible on the water system at the catchment level?	17.			
	18. Have any of the responsibilities or resources changed over time or are likely to change in the future?	18.			28.

Appendix D. Guidance for Applying the Assessment Tool

Aim and users of the tool

The GOVAQUA assessment tool aims to provide decision support by diagnosing the current status of the regime and set ambitions for a desired water governance status by identifying the factors that support or hinder the design and implementation of innovations. The primary end-users of the tool are water managers at the catchment or basin level, and other relevant stakeholders at the basin or catchment level to help them identify the strengths and weaknesses of the current water governance regime and to focus improvements of practices to the most relevant and urgent issues. When applying the tool, it is also encouraged to engage national-level stakeholders that have responsibility and decision-making power in the broader water management and governance processes.

Application process

A basic application process of the tool is to first apply it at the start of the governance innovation to assess the current state of the governance regime. Based on the results of this ex-ante assessment, the users of the tool can diagnose their current governance status, to see the most critical issues to be improved in the current regime, and to set ambitions to improve them. The second application of the tool is carried out ex-post, i.e., after the implementation of the innovation to analyse whether any positive change has been achieved through applying the new innovations in the governance regime. On the basis of this second assessment, the ambitions can be set/revised in terms of transitioning their governance regime towards sustainable and equitable water use. However, there are also other ways of applying to tool, and the use of the tool should be adapted to meet the needs of the user and their local context.

The practical application of the Excel tool itself is straightforward. The indicators are gone through one-by-one and on each indicator, the user is first asked to answer “Yes” or “No” to the questions whether the indicator is relevant for the context and whether there is sufficient data to assess the indicator. If the answer is Yes for both questions, then the user is asked to assess the state of the indicator with a four-point scale given on each indicator. Finally, the user is asked to also provide explanation for the given assessment or for the relevance/insufficiency of the data. In a case of an individual expert carrying out the assessment, the user of the tool is the expert themselves, whereas when collecting input from the stakeholder, for example in a workshop, the user is typically the facilitator of the workshop. In what follows, we provide recommendations to facilitate the application of the tool in the GOVAQUA Living Labs. Based on the experiences from testing the tool in the Living Labs, and with inspiration from other assessment approaches, we will later revise this guidance for potential users that will apply the tool in the future.

Suggestions for the practical application of the tool in the Living Labs

Preliminary assessment: The assessment criteria and indicators are recommended to be used commonly by all GOVAQUA Living Labs so that mutual exchange, learning and comparison opportunities can be maximised. However, assessing all the criteria and indicators might require a detailed analysis and data from multiple organisations. Therefore, we suggest that **the Living Lab lead partner first prepares a preliminary assessment internally and also identifies which stakeholders should be invited to assess the indicators. It may not be reasonable that all the stakeholders assess all the indicators; then it should be identified which stakeholders assess which indicators.** This assessment can then be discussed and **finalised with the stakeholders in a workshop setting**, which should also be used for **setting shared ambitions towards sustainable and equitable water use in their catchment/basin.**

Short-term vs. long-term goals of assessment: The ultimate, long-term goal of the assessment tool is to contribute to the transition to a sustainable and equitable water use. At the same time, its collaborative application in the Living Labs also has short-term benefits, such as **raising awareness and creating ownership** among the stakeholders of water governance, and **pinpointing the main governance issues** that support or hinder the innovation that is being created and tested through the Living Labs. Some of these benefits can already be achieved during the baseline description, which is recommended as the step before applying the tool for the first time.

Inclusiveness and representation: To achieve inclusive and representative results, the tool should be applied by not only the Living Lab lead partner, but a broader team representing the relevant stakeholders. Such a representation would also align with the common thread across GOVAQUA work packages, i.e., collaboration across water-using sectors and water-related disciplines. If deciding on whom to involve is not straightforward, the Living Lab lead partner can refer to the results of the stakeholder mapping that they conducted for the Living Lab. This analysis both reveals the relevant stakeholders and creates insights into several aspects within the tool, such as the criteria on recognitional and procedural justice. Depending on the number of stakeholders, the Living Lab lead partner might need to prioritise whom to involve in tool application. Specific attention should be paid to engaging “hard to reach” stakeholders, such as farmers. When the tool is applied by an inter-organizational team, this can also help ensure institutional memory by not relying on a single department or organisation for the assessment.

Ownership at the catchment/basin level: It is likely that the tool user is not the water authority at the catchment/basin level. Without the involvement of such authorities, the assessment might yield limited results, for instance due to a lack of information to score the indicators or the reluctance of stakeholders to endorse the assessment results. To **ensure a catchment-level ownership, water authorities should be engaged early on for the application of the tool.** If relevant, the ownership can be improved by involving participants from the policy level, such as local or regional governments. These measures help improve the ownership of assessment results and make them part of "the everyday work" of stakeholders.

A sound qualitative approach: Most of the criteria and indicators included in the tool are qualitative, aiming to identify the governance issues that support or hinder the innovation, and diagnosing the areas for improvement. As a result, the assessment of some indicators might not be straightforward, unless there is evidence available based on recent assessments. For instance, with indicators referring to “effectiveness”, the score can be subjective depending on the opinion of the Living Lab partners and their stakeholders. Nevertheless, such indicators should be scored using informed and reasoned judgments of tool users. For instance, involving an interdisciplinary team that brings together different types of knowledge required for assessing different criteria, can contribute to reducing personal biases in answers. To prevent divergent interpretations, each criterion also comes with a description, which guides the tool users to provide their score for the different indicators. We suggest this qualitative approach considering that the assessment capacity to quantify the necessary data is often lacking in water governance. That said, if quantitative data are available for a given indicator, they should be used to justify the score.

Continuance of the tool: The application of the assessment tool is not a once-only process. To make the best out of it, the tool users should apply it multiple times to compare the results from different applications and set their ambitions towards transitioning to sustainable and equitable water use. The decision on how often to apply the tool can be guided by the local and national policy cycles, which also potentially contributes to the relevance of the tool for policymaking. Reports from each application as well as supporting data and documents should be shared among the involved stakeholders, contributing to institutional memory.

Appendix E. Questions and Scores for Assessing the Indicators

				Indicator scale				Is the indicator relevant?	Is there sufficient data to assess the indicator?	Score*	Explanation (1-2 sentences)**
Criteria	Indicator code	Indicator title	Question for assessing the indicator	1	2	3	4				
1. State of the freshwater environment	1.1	Achievement of relevant policy requirements	What is the current status of the freshwater environment against the relevant policy requirements (WFD, EGD, SDG6, etc.)? (Can apply to surface water and/or groundwater, depending on relevant water bodies. Multiple sub-indicators - also related to pressures - can be used to assess the achievement.)	Very bad			Very good				
2. Fair sharing of data and information	2.1	Completeness of available water data and information	How available are water data and information to make well-informed decisions?	Fully unavailable			Fully available				
	2.2	Accuracy of available water data and information	How accurate is the available water-related data and information?	Fully inaccurate			Fully accurate				
	2.3	Access to water data and information	How well are the different stakeholder groups able to access water data and information? (Stakeholder groups include water user organisations, governmental and non-governmental organisations, private companies, professional organisations, academia, etc.)	Very poorly			Very well				
	2.4	Effectiveness of water information sharing	How effective is water information sharing in terms of reaching different stakeholder groups and using multiple communication channels?	Very ineffective			Very effective				

3. Distributional justice	3.1	Allocation of water resources among users	How equal is the allocation of the water resources among different users in terms of quantity, quality and timing? (Consider socio-economic differences, such as age, gender, ethnicity, income, etc., among water users)	Very unequal			Very equal				
	3.2	Access of population to safe water and sanitation	How adequate is the access of the entire population to safe water and sanitation?	Fully inadequate			Fully adequate				
	3.3	Distribution of benefits from water access among users	How fair are the benefits obtained from water access distributed among different water users?	Very unfair			Very fair				
	3.4	Distribution of costs from water access among users	How fair are the costs spent for water-related issues distributed among different water users?	Very unfair			Very fair				
	3.5	Distribution of harmful impacts among users	How equal is the distribution of harmful impacts among different water users? (Such impacts can be caused for instance by poor water quality or water pollution)	Very unequal			Very equal				
	3.6	Exposure and preparedness to water-related climate hazards	How equal is the distribution of exposure and preparedness to water-related climate hazards (such as droughts, floods or sea level rise) among water users?	Very unequal			Very equal				
4. Recognitional justice	4.1	Recognition of different water users and their needs	How adequate is the recognition of different types of water users and their needs? (Recognition can be through formal and/or informal titles, permits, agreements to define, allow, regulate, limit, etc. water use by different individuals, groups, or the environment.)	Fully inadequate			Fully adequate				

	4.2	Balance among the values and roles of water users	How balanced are the values and roles of different water users among each other? (For instance, a dominant user that views water as an economic good, or water grabbing by a specific user indicates a lack of balance.)	Full unbalanced		Full balanced				
5. Procedural justice	5.1	Representation of water users and stakeholders	How equal is the representation of different water users and other relevant stakeholders in the decision-making processes at the basin/catchment level?	Very unequal		Very equal				
	5.2	Participatory mechanisms to involve water users and stakeholders	How adequate are the participatory mechanisms to involve water users and organised stakeholders in basin/catchment management decisions?	Fully inadequate		Fully adequate				
	5.3	Representation of different types of knowledge	How well are the different types of knowledge (such as local, traditional, indigenous) as well as knowledge from different disciplines embedded in the decision-making processes at the basin/catchment level?	Very poorly		Very well				
	5.4	Involvement of water users in vulnerable conditions	How well are the water users in vulnerable conditions (such as women, elderly, disabled and minorities) involved in basin/catchment management decisions?	Very poorly		Very well				
	5.5	Transparency of decision-making processes in the water sector	How transparent are the decision-making processes in the water sector to water users in terms of the clarity and justification of the reasoning behind the decisions?	Very vague		Very transparent				
	5.6	Accountability of decision-makers in the water sector	How well are the decision-makers of the water sector being held accountable for their decisions?	Very poorly		Very well				

6. Financial efficiency and effectiveness	6.1	Economic value of water investments	How much economic value is created by the funding allocated to water investments?	Very little			Very much				
	6.2	Non-economic value of water investments	How much non-economic value, such as social or ecological benefits, is created by the funding allocated to water investments?	Very little			Very much				
	6.3	Financing available for different water uses	How much financing is available for improving multiple water uses including both human needs and ecological functions?	Very little			Very much				
7. Institutional capacity	7.1	Resources and capacity of stakeholders in water governance	How much resources and capacities do the stakeholders in water governance have for water-related issues? (Consider aspects such as number of staff, staff turnover, educational levels, trainings, etc.)	Very little			Very much				
	7.2	Leadership of responsible organisations in water governance	How well do the responsible organisations take the leadership in terms of enhancing sustainable and equitable water use?	Very poorly			Very well				
	7.3	Ownership of water-related problems by different stakeholders	How well do the different stakeholders in the public and private sectors demonstrate an ownership of water-related problems?	Very poorly			Very well				
8. Horizontal and vertical coordination	8.1	Coordination among organisations in water-using sectors	How well is the decision making coordinated among the organisations that are active in water-using sectors?	Very poorly			Very well				
	8.2	Coordination among multiple levels of water governance	How well is the decision/policy making and research coordinated among the local, regional and national levels of governance?	Very poorly			Very well				

	8.3	Fit between administrative and hydrological levels	How well does the division of administrative decision-making match with the hydrological division to different basins?	Very poorly		Very well				
	8.4	Consideration of external actors and factors in water governance	How well are the actors, drivers, pressures and impacts beyond the watershed taken into consideration in water governance?	Very poorly		Very well				
9. Enabling policy mix	9.1	Completeness of policy instruments	How well do the current policy instruments address the different aspects of the governance problem, for instance regarding multiple sectors, or through regulatory, economic and participatory approaches?	Very poorly		Very well				
	9.2	Effectiveness of policy instruments	How effective are the current policy instruments in terms of solving the governance problem in question?	Very ineffective		Very effective				
	9.3	Coherence among the policy instruments	How well are the current policy instruments aligned with each other, for instance by having goals that support or do not contradict each other?	Very poorly		Very well				

* Please choose a score if the indicator is relevant for the governance innovation and if there is sufficient data to assess the indicator.

** Please explain the chosen score. In case the indicator is irrelevant or there is no sufficient data, please also provide an explanation.